

Supplementary Material

Paper #843

A Datasets

A.1 *GlyphOnly Training Data Transformation*

In this section, we will provide a comprehensive guide on how to convert an existing dataset into a format suitable for GlyphOnly training. For the IC13, IC15, MLT17, and MLT19 datasets, we employed the Lama to perform erasure on regions with detection and recognition annotations. After evaluating the erased backgrounds using our assessment module, we will retain the high-quality backgrounds and manually select them through human intervention to create the dataset used for training. Due to the lack of recognition annotations in the SCUT-EnsText dataset, it will be processed together with the generated data using OCR API to obtain the annotations. We will only retain annotations with recognition confidence scores greater than 90%. Then, the same processing approach as real data will be applied. After obtaining the erased backgrounds and OCR annotation results, we employed the Adaptive Text Block Exploration Strategy to obtain the final dataset format required for training.

A.2 *SynthGlyph*

The source backgrounds originate from 5k synthetic sources and 5k real ones. The generated background is shown in Figure 1. The real backgrounds include RCTW, ReCTS, TD500, COCO-text, and a small subset of suitable text-generating backgrounds from SynthText. Then, using our position selection method and visual text blending method, we obtained the final dataset called SynthGlyph. The visualization of SynthGlyph is shown in Figure 2.

B Implementation Details

Training of GlyphOnly We initialize the model with parameters from Stable-Diffusion-v1-5 and employ the parameters from CLIP’s image encoder for initializing our image encoder. We load the pre-trained ABINet trained on MJSynth and SynthText datasets, as well as the text segmenter module trained on the SynthText dataset. We set the batch size to 32 and train the model for 60 epochs. We utilize the AdamW optimizer and set the learning rate to $1e-5$. During training, we mask the textual regions with a probability of 90%. During the inference stage, we will set the number of timesteps to 30 and the seed to 28.

Scene Text Detection During the pre-training stage, we adopt DB-Net as our detector with training from scratch. We utilize Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) as the optimizer with a learning rate of 0.007, a momentum of 0.9, and a weight decay of $1e-4$. The training process comprises 100,000 iterations. Testing is conducted every

625 iterations, and the highest test result obtained during this process is selected. In the fine-tuning stage, we train for 1200 epochs and conduct testing at the end of each epoch.

C Text Image Editing

Figure 3 illustrates the text editing capabilities of our method, demonstrating its strong performance in text editing. However, the generative text editing style is derived from the surrounding text. In the case of the fourth column, where the text forms a distinct style on its own, although the tampering may be difficult to detect, the original style is not preserved. To address this issue, we explored a distinctive editing strategy that does not require training. We addressed the generative text editing challenge by performing self-concatenation of the text regions, and combining them into a text block. This concatenation can take the form of $1*2$, $2*1$, $2*2$, or $3*3$ arrangements. Figure 4 demonstrates our concatenation strategy, where one of the text regions is masked for editing. This approach provides a novel direction for tackling generative text editing.

D Text Image Customization

In this section, we will demonstrate our customization capabilities for images. Figure 5 showcases our ability to generate images that perfectly match the given textual description based on a provided prompt. Unlike whole-image text generation, the generated images will not contain any unexpected additional text.

Figure 1. Visualization of the generated background.

Figure 2. Visualization of the SynthGlyph dataset. The first two rows of images represent real backgrounds, while the last two rows of images represent generated backgrounds.

Figure 3. Visual representation of text editing task.

Figure 4. A training-free generative editing strategy specifically designed for editing unique and stylistic text.

Figure 5. The visualization showcases the capability of our text blending method in text image customization.